

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

INTERNATIONAL PROGRAM COMMITTEE

Chairman:

Umarov A.A. – First Vice-Rector for Academic Affairs, UWED

Deputy Chairs:

Raimova G. M. – Professor, Head of Department, UWED

Rasulov A. S. – Professor, UWED

Bakoev M. T. – Academic Director of the Tashkent Branch of MGIMO.

Program Committee Members:

Formanov Sh. K. – Academician, AS of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Uzbekistan)

Aripov M. M. – Professor, NUUZ (Uzbekistan)

Shadimetov Kh. M. – Professor, Tashkent State Technical University

Aloev R. – Professor, NUUZ (Uzbekistan)

Khayotov A. R. – Professor, Institute of Mathematics, Academy of Sciences (Uzbekistan)

Khudoyberganov M. O. – Professor, NUUZ (Uzbekistan)

Sharipov O. Sh. – NUUZ (Uzbekistan)

Eshkuvvatov Z. K. – Professor, National Research University TIAME (Uzbekistan)

Kobulov A. V. – Professor, NUUZ (Uzbekistan)

Mascagni M. – Professor, Florida State University (USA)

Li Y. – Professor, Old Dominion University (USA)

Gemma M. – Professor, Vice President of Waseda University (Japan)

Nishimura Shoji – Professor, Dean of Waseda University (Japan)

Hwang C. O. – Professor, Gwangju Institute of Science and Technology (Korea)

Seitov A. Zh. – Professor, UWED (Uzbekistan)

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

Chairman:

Djalalov M.M. – Vice-Rector for Digital Transformation and Economy, UWED

Deputy Chairs:

Raimova G. M. – Head of the Department of System Analysis and Mathematical Modelling, UWED

Bakoev M. T. – Academic Director of the Tashkent Branch of MGIMO

Organizing Committee Members:

Abdullaev E.E. (Dean, UWED, Uzbekistan)

Dalabaev U. (UWED, Uzbekistan)

Siddiqova M. (UWED, Uzbekistan)

Seitov A. Zh. UWED, Uzbekistan)

CONFERENCE SECRETARIAT

Umarova Sh.G. (Head of the Secretariat), Buriev A., Kasimova N.J., Maraimova K. Sh., Khasanova D.R.,
Yarashev I., Solaeva M., Mustafakulova A. Kh., Akabirkhodjaeva D.R.

International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

On a linear inverse problem with nonlocal boundary conditions for a three-dimensional equation of mixed type of the second kind of the fourth order in a parallelepiped.

Sirojiddin Dzhamaalov¹, Bakhtiyor Khalkhadzhaev², Sherzod Yusupov³

V.I.Romanovskiy Institute of Mathematics, Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences^{1,3}

*Tashkent Institute of Management and Economics*²

siroj63@mail.ru, xalkadjaev@timeedu.uz, sherzod.yusupov.2020@inbox.ru

Keywords: three-dimensional equation of mixed type of the second kind of the fourth order, linear inverse problem with nonlocal boundary conditions, correctness of the problem, Fourier method, methods of " ε -regularization a priori estimates, sequence of approximations.

1. Introduction

In the process of studying nonlocal problems, a close relationship was revealed between problems with nonlocal boundary conditions and inverse problems. By now, inverse problems for classical equations such as parabolic, elliptic and hyperbolic types of the second order have been studied quite well [1],[2]. Linear inverse problems for equations of mixed type of the second order in the plane have been studied in the works of A.G. Megrabov, K.B. Sabitov and their students [3],[4].

For three-dimensional equations of mixed type of both first and second kind of the second order, they were studied in the works of S.Z. Dzhamaalov, and for multidimensional equations of mixed type of the second order of both first and second kind with local and non-local conditions in bounded domains, they were studied and developed in the works of S.Z. Dzhamaalov, R.R. Ashurov and S.Z. Dzhamaalov, S.G. Pyatkov [5]-[8].

For high-order mixed-type equations, such problems have not been studied in practice. We will try to partially fill this gap in this paper.

In this paper, for the study of unique solvability of inverse problems for a three-dimensional equation of mixed type of the second kind, fourth order in a rectangle, a new method is proposed. Which is based on reducing the inverse problem to direct non-local boundary value problems of periodic type for a family of loaded differential equations of mixed type of the second kind, fourth order[5]-[9].

Let us recall that a loaded equation is usually called an equation with partial derivatives that contains in the coefficients or on the right-hand side the values of certain functionals from the solution of the equation [10].

In the domain

$$G = (0, 1) \times (0, T) \times (0, \ell) = Q \times (0, \ell) = \{(x, t, y) : 0 < x < 1; 0 < t < T < +\infty; 0 < y < \ell\}.$$

Let's consider equations of mixed type of the second kind of the fourth order.

$$Lu = Pu + Mu + Nu = \psi(x, t, y), \quad (1)$$

where

$$Pu = \sum_{i=0}^4 K_i(x, t) D_t^i u, \quad Mu = a(x)u_{xxxx} - b(x)u_{xxtt} - c(x)u_{xx}, \quad Nu = u_{yyyy}.$$

Here, $(K_4(x, t) = K_4(t), K_4(0) = K_4(T) = 0; a(x) > 0, b(x) > 0, c(x) > 0$ and $D_t^i u = \frac{\partial^i u}{\partial t^i}$, where $i = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4$.

Equation (1) refers to mixed-type equations of the second kind, since no restrictions are imposed on the sign of the function $K_4(t)$ with respect to the variable t inside the segment $[0, T]$ [11].

In the future, we will assume that $\psi(x, t, y) = g(x, t, y) + h(x, t) \cdot f(x, t, y)$, where $g(x, t, y)$ and $f(x, t, y)$ are given functions, and the function $h(x, t)$ is subject to definition.

Linear inverse problem. Find functions $\{u(x, t, y), h(x, t)\}$, satisfying equation (1) in the domain G , such that the function $u(x, t, y)$ satisfies the following nonlocal boundary conditions:

$$\gamma D_t^q u|_{t=0} = D_t^q u|_{t=T}, \quad q = 0, 1, 2 \quad (2)$$

$$\rho D_x^p u|_{x=0} = D_x^p u|_{x=1}, \quad p = 0, 1, 2, 3 \quad (3)$$

$$u|_{y=0} = u|_{y=1} = 0; u_{yy}|_{y=0} = u_{yy}|_{y=\ell} = 0 \quad (4)$$

and an additional condition

$$u(x, t, \ell_0) = \varphi_0(x, t), \quad \text{where } 0 < \ell_0 < \ell < +\infty \quad (5)$$

and together with the functions $h(x, t)$ belongs to the class

$$U = \{(u, h) \mid u \in W_2^{4,3}(G), h \in W_2^4(Q)\}.$$

Here, by $W_2^{4,3}(G)$ we denote the anisotropic Sobolev space with the norm

$$\|u\|_{W_2^{4,3}(G)}^2 = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\ell}} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (1 + \mu_k^4)^3 \|u_k(x, t)\|_{W_2^4(Q)}^2,$$

where the functions $u_k(x, t)$, $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, are the Fourier coefficients of the function $u(x, t, y)$ with respect to the system $Y_k(y) = \{\sqrt{2\ell^{-1}} \sin \mu_k y\}$, $\mu_k = \pi k \ell^{-1}$, $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$,

and by $W_2^l(Q)$ we denote the Sobolev space with the norm

$$\|\vartheta\|_{W_2^l(Q)}^2 = \sum_{|\alpha| \leq l} \int_Q |D^\alpha \vartheta|^2 dx dt,$$

where α is a multi-index and D^α is the generalized derivative with respect to the variables x and t .

We will assume the following conditions are satisfied. Let all coefficients of equation (1) be sufficiently smooth functions in the domain \overline{Q} , and let the following conditions hold with respect to the coefficients, the right-hand side, and the given function $\varphi_0(x, t)$:

Condition 1: Non-local condition

$$K_{4t}(0) = K_{4t}(T); \quad K_i(x, 0) = K_i(x, T); \quad i = 0, 2, 3, \quad \forall x \in [0, 1],$$

$$\gamma g(x, 0, z) = g(x, T, z), \quad \gamma f(x, 0, z) = f(x, T, z).$$

$$K_1(x, t) > 0, \quad K_3(x, t) > 0$$

are sufficiently large functions. In addition, let the following conditions be met for the coefficients of equation (1):

$$-(2K_3 + (2j - 3)K_{4t} + 3\lambda K_4) \geq \delta_3 > 0, \quad j = 0, 1, 2;$$

$$2K_1 - K_{2t} + \lambda K_2 \geq \delta_2 > 0, \quad \lambda K_0 - K_{0t} \geq \delta_1 > 0,$$

for any $(x, t) \in \bar{Q}$, where $\lambda = \frac{2}{T} \ln |\gamma| > 0$, $|\gamma| > 1$, $|\rho| \geq 1$.

$$a(x) \geq a_0 > 0, \quad b(x) \geq b_0 > 0, \quad c(x) \geq c_0 > 0.$$

Smoothness:

$$g(x, t, l_0) = g_0(x, t) \in C_{x,t}^{0,1}(\bar{Q}), \quad f(x, t, l_0) = f_0(x, t) \in C_{x,t}^{0,1}(\bar{Q}),$$

$$|f_0(x, t)| \geq \eta > 0, \quad f \in W_2^{3,3}(G), \quad g \in W_2^{1,3}(G).$$

Condition 2:

$$\varphi_0(x, t) \in W_2^5(Q); \quad \gamma D_t^q \varphi_0|_{t=0} = D_t^q \varphi_0|_{t=T}, \quad q = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4;$$

$$\rho D_x^p \varphi_0|_{x=0} = D_x^p \varphi_0|_{x=1}, \quad p = 0, 1, 2, 3, \rho \geq 1$$

Theorem 1. The main result. *Let the above listed conditions 1 and 2 be satisfied for the coefficients of equation (1), and let there exist a positive number σ such that for some (arbitrarily small) positive constants the following relations hold: $\delta_0 - 31 e^{\lambda T} \sigma^{-1} = \delta > 0$, $q = M \cdot \sigma \cdot \|f\|_{W_2^{3,3}(G)}^2 < 1$, (where $\delta_0 = \min\{\delta_3, \lambda a_0, \lambda b_0, \lambda c_0, \delta_2, \delta_1\}$, M is a positive constant). Then there exists a unique solution to the linear inverse problem (1)-(5) from the specified class U .*

References

1. Yu. E. Anikanov. *Some methods of studying multidimensional inverse problems for differential equations*. Novosibirsk: Nauka, 1978, 120 p.
2. A. V. Bitsadze. On the incorrectness of the Dirichlet problem for equations of mixed type. *Doklady Akademii Nauk SSSR*. Vol. 122, No. 4, 1953, pp. 167–170.
3. A. G. Megrabov. Some inverse problems for an equation of mixed type. *Doklady Akademii Nauk SSSR*. Vol. 234, 1977, pp. 305–307.
4. K. B. Sabitov, N. V. Martemyanova. Nonlocal inverse problem for a mixed type equation. *Izv. universities. Mathematics*. 2011. No. 2. pp. 71–85.
5. S. Z. Dzhamalov. *Nonlocal boundary value and inverse problems for equations of mixed type*. Monograph. Tashkent, 2021, 176 p.

6. S. Z. Dzhamalov, R. R. Ashurov. On one linear inverse problem for a multidimensional equation of mixed type of the second kind, second order. *Differential Equations*. Vol. 55, No. 1, 2019, pp. 34–44.
7. S. Z. Dzhamalov, R. R. Ashurov. On one linear inverse problem for a multidimensional equation of mixed type of the first kind, second order. *News of Universities. Mathematics*. 2019, No. 6, pp. 1–12.
8. S. Z. Dzhamalov, S. G. Pyatkov. Some classes of inverse problems for second-order equations of mixed type. *Mathematical Notes of NEFU*. Vol. 25, No. 4, 2018, pp. 3–15.
9. S. Z. Dzhamalov, B. B. Khalkhadzhaev. On the smoothness of a generalized solution of a semi-nonlocal boundary value problem for a fourth-order equation. *Journal of Contemporary Applied Mathematics*. Vol. 14, No. 2, 2024, pp. 107–120.
10. A. M. Nakhushhev. *Loaded equations and their application*. Moscow: Nauka, 2012.
11. V. N. Vragov. *Boundary value problems for non-classical equations of mathematical physics*. Novosibirsk: NGU, 1983.

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

Bosishga ruxsat etildi: 10.01.2026-yil.
Bichimi 70x100 1/16, "Times New Roman"
garniturada raqamli bosma usulida bosildi.
Shartli bosma tabog'i: 28,5. Adadi: 100.

"Noble Print" MChJ bosmaxonasida chop etildi.
100194, Toshkent shahri, Yunusobod-11, 62-uy.